

MICROMECHANICS MODELING OF TENSILE/SHEAR BEHAVIOR AND CRACK DENSITY OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

D. Haruyama¹, S. Onodera², and T. Okabe³

¹ Engine Technology Department, IHI Corporation, daichi_haruyama@ihi.co.jp
² Department of Aerospace Engineering, Tohoku University, sonodera@plum.mech.tohoku.ac.jp
³ Department of Aerospace Engineering, Tohoku University, okabe@plum.mech.tohoku.ac.jp

Background

Intermediate materials

Microstructure [10]

Motivation

- We want to
- ✓ predict the mechanical property of composite material.
 - ✓ describe macro stiffness degradation from micro damages.

Objective We evaluate the relationship between damages and stiffness degradation of brittle matrix composites.

Micromechanics model and damage variable

Tensile damage

Matrix crack [4]

- ✓ Model proposed by Curtin et al.
- ✓ Transition of nonlinear behavior by the condition of debonding

Transverse crack [5][6]

- ✓ Model proposed by Okabe et al
- ✓ Load is supported by surrounding materials
- ✓ Material property: Homogeneous anisotropy

Calculation of $[d_i(\rho_i, \epsilon_i)]$ from micromechanics model

x_i : Crack space, ρ_i : Crack density ($\rho_i = 1/\bar{x}_i$), σ_i : Stress, ϵ_i : Strain, d_i : Damage variable, τ : Sliding stress

Shear damage [7]

$$(1 - d_{ij})^{-1} = \frac{1}{2} \{ (1 - d_i)^{-1} + (1 - d_j)^{-1} \} \quad (i \neq j)$$

It is possible to calculate the shear behavior from tensile behavior

Stress-strain behavior

$$\{\sigma\} = [M]^{-1} [D_0] \{\epsilon\}$$

This equation is based on continuum damage mechanics.

$[M]$: Damage effect matrix, $[D_0]$: Elastic modulus matrix

- [4] W. A. Curtin et al., Acta Materialia, Vo. 46, No.10, 1998.
 [5] Tomonaga Okabe et al., International Journal of Damage Mechanics, Vol. 27, No. 6, 2018.
 [6] PETER GUDMUNDSON et al., International Journal of Solids and Structures, Vol. 30, No. 23, 1993
 [7] C. Chow, et al., Engineering Fracture Mechanics, Vol.34, No.3, 1989.

Damage evolution [9]

Crack area and position

Γ_i : Energy release rate, U : Elastic strain energy, σ_{ci} : Critical stress, Γ_{ci} : Fracture energy, b_i, w_i : Crack length, $2x_i$: Evaluation length, A_i : Crack area

[9] S. Onodera, et al., Advanced Composite Materials, Vol.26, No.5, 2017.

Assumption

- ✓ Work is 0 from external loading
- ✓ Periodic cracks
- ✓ New crack position is center ($t=0.5$)

$$\Gamma(\rho_i) = - \frac{U_a(\rho_i) - U_b(\rho_i/2)}{A_i}$$

where $\rho_i = 1/x_i$

Crack initiation criteria

$$\sigma_i \geq \sigma_{ci}$$

Crack growth criteria

$$\Gamma_i = \Gamma_{ci}$$

Crack density ρ_i is evaluated as above equation is satisfied

Crack length in these models

- ✓ Crack length increases with increasing crack density
- ✓ Average crack length b_i was used because of equally distributed cracks.

$b_i(2x_i)$: Crack length before new crack initiation
 $b_i(x_i)$: Crack length after new crack initiation

Calculation example

- ✓ These models were implemented in subroutine of Abaqus.
- ✓ Not only tensile behavior but also shear behavior can be calculated with these model.

Comparison of the paper and these models

Verification by calculation in transverse direction

Paper [9]

- ✓ Input strain is only ϵ_2 because of formulation in 1 dimension

These model

- ✓ Input strain is not only ϵ_2 but also ϵ_1 ($= -\nu_{21}\epsilon_2$) and ϵ_3 ($= -\nu_{23}\epsilon_2$).

- ✓ These models have a good agreement in the paper results [9].

Validation by comparison of experimental results and calculation

- ✓ These models have a good agreement in the experimental results before the inflection point which is the crack saturation [10].

Material parameters are experimental material properties or calibrated as stress-strain nonlinear behaviour of the numerical analysis agrees with the test result.

Future work These model will be applied to the composite materials such as the cross-ply laminates and the woven fabric for the validation